

BENEFITS

- Equal insulation performance as existing wood-based products
- Very **light weight**, no training need for assembly
- Made from **renewable wood pulp**
- Recycled wood can be utilized as a raw material
- **Lowers** greenhouse gas **emissions** and **stores CO₂** in building walls
- **Easy** recycling and use in circular economy value chains (if suitable fire retardant is used)

Project innovation fact sheet

Wood Pulp Panels

Fibre panels for thermal building insulation

APPLICATION

- Thermal insulation material as core layer of Structural Insulation Panels (SIP) for building walls
- **Many applications** of similar conventional materials (e.g., glass wool)

NEXT STEPS

- Increasing strength for structural applications
- Upscaling of production
- Other applications e.g., acoustic panels, wind protective panels, cushioning material (e.g., packaging)

